

Development of multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor for simultaneous strain and temperature monitoring for composite manufacturing process

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ABSTRACT

Coaxial structured fibers have gained significant attention in sensor applications due to their design flexibility and ability to enable multi-functionality. However, when utilized for strain monitoring in composite manufacturing processes, the sensor's complex and thicker structure can lead to stress concentration and signal interference. To address this issue, we propose a multifunctional coaxial fiber sensor capable of simultaneous temperature and strain measurement during composite manufacturing process. To achieve multi-functional sensing, we employ a multi-shell structure consisting of a multi-conductive layer and PEDOT:PSS layer, applied to a creep-enhanced ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene core fiber using a simple dip-coating method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite materials are fabricated by physically mixing reinforcing fibers and polymer matrix, resulting in enhanced mechanical properties. However, a significant challenge arises from the mismatch of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the fiber and the matrix[1]. At the macroscopic level, this CTE mismatch leads to warpage and distortion of the structure after the curing reaction. At a microscopic level, during the cooling stage of the composite manufacturing process, there is a possibility of interfacial debonding between the fiber and matrix, which can degrade the material properties of the composite[2]. Therefore, it is crucial to employ real-time strain and temperature monitoring during the manufacturing process of composite structures to reduce residual stress by optimizing the curing cycle.

Conductive particle-reinforced nanocomposite sensors offer a potential solution due to their design flexibility[3]. Over the years, numerous studies have focused on developing multi-functional or multimodal sensors capable of detecting multiple physical signals in a single device[4]. For instance, Saeidi-Javash et al. developed printable multi-functional sensors that utilize MXene and graphene nanosheets to measure both strain and temperature[5]. Zhao et al. fabricated a flexible multi-functional sensor using thermosensitive platinum ribbons and a flexible polyimide substrate to measure pressure and temperature stimuli[6]. Xu et al. demonstrated bio-inspired electronic skins that employ gold/thermoplastic polyurethane/cellulose membrane to measure multiple signals, including temperature, electroencephalogram, and electrocardiogram[7]. Xue et al. developed a flexible dual-parameter sensor array using PDMS-MXene/CNT piezoresistors and PDMS-MXene thermistors to detect pressure and temperature, respectively[8]. However, most of these studies have primarily focused on developing flexible sensors for healthcare or wearable applications. Moreover,

conventional multimodal sensors face two limitations when applied to composite monitoring applications: a usable temperature range that is too low compared to the curing temperature of composite materials (~ 125 °C) and a thickness and size that are too large to embed into composite structures. This is because most research implements the multimodal function through the stacking or arraying of sensing elements.

In this work, we present a multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor capable of simultaneously measuring the strain through resistance changes in the multi-conductive layer and temperature through thermoelectric voltage changes at the junction between multi-conductive layer and poly-ethylenedioxythiophene:poly-styrenesulphonate (PEDOT:PSS) layer during the composite cure process. The ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) core fiber and multi-conductive layer was fabricated using a dry-jet wet spinning with a microwave-assisted cross-linking method, as well as a dip-coating process based on our previous works. To create the junction point between multi-conductive layer and PEDOT:PSS layer, laser etching was employed to effectively remove a partial area of the outer polyurethane (PU) layer and expose the multi-conductive layer. The surface morphologies and damage on the multi-conductive layer after the etching process were investigated using an optical microscope and Raman spectroscopy, respectively. Furthermore, strain sensitivity (i.e. gauge factor) measurement and cyclic tests were performed under various strain ranges using electronic test equipment to examine the effect of junction fabrication and PEDOT:PSS coating. The thermoelectric voltage change was investigated under various temperature and strain ranges.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Fabrication of core fiber

The UHMWPE fibers was fabricated by using a dry-jet wet spinning method with 4 wt.% spinning solution at a lab-scale spinning instrument (Wet spinning system, DISSOL, Republic of Korea) as shown in Figure 1. The spinning solution was fed to the 0.65 mm diameter of spinneret under 170 °C. The UHMWPE fibers were formed by solidification of the polymer solution extruded from the spinneret in a coagulation bath containing distilled water at 25 °C. The residual solvent after solidification process was removed by rinsing process using hexane (Sigma-Aldrich Inc., USA) for 24 h at 25 °C. The hot-stretching process was introduced to enhance the initial crystallinity of the as-spun UHMWPE fibers. The stretching ratio and treatment temperature was adjusted by 14 and 120 °C, respectively.

Figure 1: Dry-jet wet spinning of UHMWPE core fibers.

2.1 Dip coating processes

Figure 2 shows the schematic configuration of the multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor consisting of the following sequence from the core: UHMWPE core fiber for load bearing, 1st PU layer, MWCNT

conductive layer for strain sensing, 2nd PU layer. A role of the double PU layers is to reduce the noise level and enhance the linearity of the fiber sensor by preventing failure of electrical networks. This sensing layer was fabricated by the dip coating processes. At first, the UHMWPE core fiber was submerged into the aqueous PU solution (CRP 26301, T&L Co., Ltd., Republic of Korea) and withdrawn from the bath after 20 sec. Subsequently, the PU coated fiber was dried at 80 °C for 3 min and this process was repeated in 3-times. Thereafter, the electrically conductive layer was formed on the PU coated UHMWPE fiber by using the same method with the aqueous MWCNT solution (K-Nanos 100P, Kumho petrochemical Co., Ltd., Republic of Korea). In the case of the sandwich-structured multi-conductive layer to improve sensitivity and linearity from the combination of varying concentration of MWCNT, the same coating procedures were adopted from the bottom layer of 3 wt.% MWCNT, the middle layer of 2 wt.% MWCNT, and the top layer of 3 wt.% MWCNT, respectively. The thickness of each conductive layers was controlled by varying the number of the dip coating process to minimize the variation of resistance due to the thickness change. Subsequently, the conductive layer coated UHMWPE fiber was dried in a 60 °C oven for 1 hour to remove excessive water in the MWCNT conductive layer. Lastly, 2nd PU layer was coated with the same procedure of the 1st PU layer.

Figure 2: Schematics of multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor

2.2 Sensing performance of multi-functional coaxial fiber sensors

Figure S7a shows the schematic diagram for measuring the relative resistance change ($\Delta R/R_0$) and relative thermoelectric voltage change ($\Delta V/V_0$). These signals were simultaneously measured using LCR meter (E4980A, Keysight Technologies, USA) and high-precision multimeter (DMM6500, Keithley Instruments LLC., USA), and the signal measurement equipment was controlled by LabView (LabView 2022, National Instruments Corp., USA). To avoid signal interference, resistance was measured by an AC-based signal with a 1,200 Hz frequency, and the thermoelectric voltage was measured by a DC-based signal. The relative resistance change under static and cyclic loading conditions was measured using an LCR meter and universal testing machine (INSTRON 5969, Illinois Tool Works Inc., USA). The repeatability of the bimodal coaxial fiber sensor was estimated by measuring the changes in the resistance during the cyclic tensile test with 2.0 mm/min⁻¹ crosshead speed under 10, 20, 30, and 40% of the failure strain of the bimodal coaxial fiber sensors.

Figure 3: Measurement for sensing performance of coaxial fiber sensor

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Surface morphologies of multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor

Figure 4 presents the surface morphologies and cross-section images of PEDOT:PSS layer-coated fiber sensors. FE-SEM and EDS mapping images confirmed that the PEDOT:PSS layer was effectively coated on fiber sensor. The cross-section images of the multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor in Figure 4b confirmed the multilayer structure from the core fiber to the 3rd PU layer with respect to the coating sequence.

Figure 4: Coating thickness and cross-section images of multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor

3.2 Sensing performances

The repeatability with various strain ranges from 10% to 40% of the failure strain of the bimodal coaxial fiber sensor, shown in Figure 5, confirmed that the resistance change from the multi-conductive layer can be stably measured over various strain ranges without degradation by the PEDOT:PSS layer.

Figure 5: Repeatability of sensor fibers under various strain ranges

Figure 6 shows the monitoring results of the thermoelectric voltage and relative resistance change during a stepwise temperature cycle ranging from 35 to 125 °C, with 30 °C increments, to investigate the simultaneous measurement of these parameters without signal interference. The results indicated that both the thermoelectric voltage and resistance could be measured simultaneously without any signal interference. Therefore, it can be concluded that the bimodal coaxial fiber sensor can be applied to composite manufacturing processes without the need for an additional compensation process to correct thermoelectric voltage measurement errors resulting from external strain.

Figure 6: Measurement of sensing performance of multi-functional coaxial fiber sensor.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a multi-layer structured coaxial fiber sensor was introduced to simultaneously measure the temperature and strain. The effects of bimodal coaxial fiber sensors were investigated by measurement of surface morphologies, sensing response change which is including static and cyclic deformation, and monitoring of temperature and strain signal.

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